

The Soviet-Afghan War: Causes, Impacts and Lessons

Abstract:

The Soviet Invasion of Afghanistan was one of the many proxy conflicts fought between the United States and the Soviet Union during the Cold War. While this conflict eventually became a proxy battleground, the primary causes of the war were mainly internal or regional. In the war, armed militias managed to defeat the mighty Soviet Union military, with its superior weapons and training. The war, which was initially supposed to be a short military intervention, carried on for a decade. It contributed to growing dissatisfaction with the government within the Soviet Union and encouraged fringe factions in Afghanistan to promulgate their extremist ideas to carry out a religious struggle against a common enemy for the supposed greater good. The Soviet Union's involvement in Afghanistan poses some important questions. First, did the Soviet Union have sufficient strategic interests to invade Afghanistan in the late 1970s? How did the Red Army get defeated by a group of largely disunited guerilla forces? What were the impacts of the war on the Soviet Union itself and how did the invasion contribute to the rise of global terror? To answer these questions, this essay will examine cables, documents, biographies, and papers from academics on both sides of the conflict, to develop a complete understanding of the myriad of factors that shaped the events of the war. The essay also briefly examines the military phases of the war and the evolution of Soviet military doctrine in Afghanistan, as well as the tactics used by

the *Mujahideen* forces. In order to establish the causes of the war, an account of the history of Afghanistan has been presented, with a special emphasis on Soviet-Afghan relations. In so analysing, the essay presents a thesis that the events of the Soviet-Afghan War were driven primarily by regional factors and were only exacerbated by foreign influence. In concluding the essay, military observations, learnings, and general observations about the rise of Islamic fundamentalism during the war have been commented on. The essay aims to present a comprehensive account of the Soviet-Afghan War from the lens of both, the Soviets and the Coalition forces at the political, military, and socio-economic levels.

Introduction:

The Cold War was arguably one of the most significant conflicts of the 20th century that resulted in at least over 10 million casualties all around the world resulting from numerous genocides, military interventions, and civil wars waged directly or indirectly by the two main hegemons of the era: the United States and the Soviet Union.¹ Following the Cuban Missile Crisis in 1962, the threat of nuclear war paved the way for a temporary detente to be reached between the aggressors of the conflict from 1969 to 1979. This period of improvement in relations between the USSR and the USA took the form of numerous treaties, such as the SALT (The Strategic Arms Limitation Talks) treaties, signed between the two countries to control the use of arms (in particular nuclear weapons) and to ensure the security of Europe.² However, the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan in 1979 led to a sudden halt in the warming of diplomatic relations between the two countries. This invasion was primarily a result of ongoing political strife in the country that endangered Soviet interests in the region.

Since the time of the Silk Route, Afghanistan has been of great geopolitical value due to its location at the crossroads of Central Asia, South Asia, and the Middle East. Afghanistan had a long history of circumventing colonial rule, and the country itself consisted of ethnically diverse groups—the Pashtuns, Uzbeks, Tajiks, Hazaras and 21 minor ethnic groups—ruled by a Monarch.³ Afghanistan and the Soviet Union had maintained good relations since 1919 and the Soviets were the first to recognise Afghanistan following the Third Anglo-Afghan War and the Treaty of Rawalpindi, which affirmed Afghanistan’s sovereignty.⁴ The Soviet Union had also given military aid to the Afghan government, and played a major role in the rise of the People’s Democratic Party of Afghanistan (PDPA), which established a Marxist system in the country. However, in the late 1970s, Soviet leaders were concerned that Hafizullah Amin, the leader of the PDPA and the president of Afghanistan, was a US agent.⁵ These suspicions culminated in the invasion in December 1979. The war was a sizable drain on the Soviet economy, with Mikhail Gorbachev, the President of the Soviet Union, referring to the war as a “bleeding wound.”⁶ The invasion also contributed to the collapse of the Soviet Union, 2 years after its end. On the military front, the invasion exposed cracks in the Red Army’s counterinsurgency strategy against the *Mujahideen* fighting in the rural regions of Afghanistan. These *Mujahideen* fighters were secretly supported by Pakistani and United States intelligence services under Operation Cyclone, during which the Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) supplied rural tribesmen with arms to fight against the Soviet Army. Following the Soviet withdrawal, many of these Mujahideen organised themselves into radical Islamist *jihadist* groups. These groups fought the Afghan civil war amongst themselves to establish supremacy, which ultimately led to the Taliban forming a government in Afghanistan. The invasion, which was the first major Soviet military operation outside Europe, also had wide-reaching consequences that continue to affect the security and stability of the country to date.

Causes for the Invasion:

The Soviet invasion of Afghanistan was not the direct product of a single event but a consequence of multiple factors that compounded over time. On receipt of the Gromyko, Andropov, Ustinov, and Ponamarev report titled “The Situation in Afghanistan,”⁷ the attention of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union’s Politburo shifted towards the situation in Afghanistan, and on December 24, 1979, the invasion was launched. The official cause for the invasion, as given by the Politburo on December 31st, was to “ease the pace of Afghanistan’s communist revolution and thereby protect the communist (PDPA) regime from collapsing due to its domestic unpopularity, thereby ceding to Islamist and Western forces.”⁸ The primary causes of the invasion can be divided into four main categories: 1) Soviet strategic interests in Afghanistan, 2) the Political Situation in Afghanistan, 3) The Brezhnev Doctrine and 4) The preservation of the Soviet sphere of influence.

1. Strategic Interests in Afghanistan: Afghanistan being located at the centre of Asia is of extreme geopolitical value. The region is often seen as a gateway to Central Asia, and the British Empire, recognising this strategic importance, fought three Anglo-Afghan wars to gain control of the region. In addition to this, Afghanistan is also endowed with rich mineral resources. In 1978, the World Bank estimated that oil reserves in Afghanistan were only 10 million barrels, but people who defected from Afghanistan believed that the reserves were twice the official amount. The country also had significant reserves of natural gas, which were being supplied to Soviet Central Asia at less than one-fifth the commercial cost. This exploitation of natural resources, which had been happening since 1968, continued during the Soviet invasion, and by 1980, not a single cubic metre of natural gas was being used in Afghanistan itself.⁹ Furthermore, the invasion of Afghanistan was seen

as a way for the Soviets to get access to warm water ports, which had been a Russian objective since the time of Peter the Great. The CIA also recognised the possible threat of a Soviet invasion of Iran from Afghanistan to capture a warm-water port and had identified *Chah Bahar* on the Baluchi Coast as a possible target of a Soviet attack.¹⁰ However, this theory has been criticised by many academics, including M. S. Agwani, the author of *Afghanistan in Crisis*, who wrote, "The plain truth is that the Soviets now possess a sizable, modern, and self-reliant navy whose efficacy does not depend on physical control of warm water ports."¹¹ Henry Kissinger also remarked that while it is tempting to look at Soviet policy and view it as a grand master plan, history indicates that there is often a lot of "improvisation" in Soviet policy.¹² Thus, Soviet ambitions to exploit the geographical and mineral resources of the region are a plausible cause for the invasion.

2. Political Situation in Afghanistan: Soviet Foreign Policy Following the Bolshevik Revolution was guided by the principle of *Comintern*, or Communism International, whose stated aim was to launch a "world revolution."¹³ Afghanistan had a strong *Comintern* movement that tried to launch a revolution in 1919. Afghans also took part in the Congress of Eastern People's in Baku, which was sponsored by the Comintern. In 1955, Soviet Premier Khrushchev visited Afghanistan and signed several agreements that allowed Afghan military officers and civil servants to come and undergo "professional training" in the Soviet Union.¹⁴ However, Marxist-Leninist ideology truly became popular among some factions in Afghanistan with the formation of the People's Democratic Party of Afghanistan (PDPA) in 1965.¹⁵ The PDPA was formed by Barbrak Karmal and Nur Muhammad Taraki, with the latter being elected as the first general secretary. A major

problem faced by the PDPA was the lack of an industrial working class in Afghanistan, a crucial element of Marxist- Leninist philosophy. In 1967, the PDPA split into multiple factions on account of ethno-religious and ideological differences. The *Khalq* (Masses) faction led by Taraki and the *Parcham*(Banner) faction led by Karmal became the two most popular factions. While Taraki wanted a Leninist-type party, Karmal preferred a broad national democratic front.¹⁶ In the early 1970s, the Soviets began to infiltrate the Afghan military and government with the aim of deposing the monarchy and installing a new leader. These efforts culminated in the bloodless coup d'etat of 1973, which installed Sardar Daud Khan, the former prime minister of the Monarch, Zahir Shah, as President. Daud Khan, who had earned the nickname of “Red Premier,”¹⁷ had fallen out with the King over the type of democratic system which should be adopted in the country, and had been dismissed in 1963 as he favoured a single-party system and the King saw merit in a multi-party system. A decade later, when he came back to power, Daud Khan adopted many new social reforms, which were often protested by traditional conservatives, and reasserted Afghanistan’s claim over Pakistan’s North-West Frontier Province (NWFP), which nearly drove both countries into a war.¹⁸ He wanted to improve relations with the United States while maintaining relations with Moscow, thereby adopting a policy of non-alignment.

This led to the Soviets engineering the *Saur* Revolution in April 1978 with the support of the Afghan military to topple Daud Khan and replace him with Muhammed Taraki and the PDPA.¹⁹ Taraki aimed to transform Afghanistan into a socialist state and continued to pursue policy campaigns for female literacy and other cultural reforms in spite of public backlash. During Taraki’s time, factionalism within the PDPA increased, and *Parchmites*,

including Karmal, Noor Ahmad Noor and Anahita Ratebzad, were expelled from the cabinet or posted abroad as ambassadors to consolidate the role of the *Khalq* faction in Afghanistan.²⁰ In March 1979, the frustration of the Afghan people with the communist regime resulted in the Herat Uprising, during which the 17th Afghan Infantry Division mutinied and joined the protests against the government.²¹ Following the uprising, the number of Soviet advisors, known as *Sardandoy*, in Afghanistan increased from 1000 to 5000, and Amin, the foreign minister, began to strengthen his position.²² He began to act as a liaison between the military and the government, and conflict between Amin and Taraki increased on the issue of Soviet-Afghan relations. In September 1979, after Taraki's return from a trip to Moscow, he organised a meeting with Amin, which was in reality a trap to capture or kill Amin. Amin survived this attack, arrested Taraki, and was later elected general secretary of the PDPA. Amin, possibly scared of a Soviet plot to get him ousted, killed Taraki in October.²³ This made the Soviet Union further distrust Amin, whom they saw as an unpredictable ally. Civil unrest also increased during Amin's time on account of his radical policy changes. A Soviet diplomat regarding these policy changes remarked, "The *Khalqis* had made a mistake in trying to do too many things too fast. The regime should have taken four or five years to affect what they tried to accomplish in a few months."²⁴ A combination of Amin's unpopular policies, Soviet suspicions that he was trying to collude with the Americans, and decades of political instability led to the Soviet invasion.

3. Brezhnev Doctrine: The Brezhnev Doctrine was the policy used by the Soviets to justify the invasion of Czechoslovakia during the Prague Spring in 1968 as well as the Soviet

invasion of Afghanistan in 1979.²⁵ The Brezhnev Doctrine was an instrument to protect communist parties in countries from internal or external opposition to the movement. This idea was first introduced by Brezhnev in his speech to the Polish Communist Party Conference on November 12, 1968. Towards the end of his speech to the conference, he said,

“When the internal and external forces hostile to socialism seek to halt the development of any socialist country and restore the capitalist order, when a threat to the cause of socialism in that country or a threat to the security of the socialist community as a whole emerges, this is no longer only a problem of the people of that country but also a common problem, a concern for all socialist countries.”²⁶

This policy was expounded on by Sergei Kovalyov in his article in Pravda, the communist newspaper, titled “*Sovereignty and International Duties of Socialist States*,” published on September 26, 1968. The article stated, “Each Communist Party is responsible not only to socialist countries, to the entire communist movement, but also to its own people. Whoever forgets this, in stressing only the independence of the communist party, becomes one-sided and deviates from his international duty.”²⁷ This doctrine implies that an attack on any socialist state is an attack on all Communist countries, thus authorising the use of military force to protect socialism in that country. In 1978, the 20-year Friendship, Good Neighbourliness, and Cooperation agreement signed between Taraki and Moscow implicitly warranted the use of force in case of any threat to the Communist Party in Afghanistan, thus paving the way for a Soviet invasion.

4. Preservation of the Soviet Sphere of Influence: The Soviet Union and the Russian Empire, before it, recognised the potential of Afghanistan as a buffer state to prevent external influences and powers from penetrating into the empire. From 1830 to 1907, the Russian Empire and the British Empire fought between themselves to establish control over Afghanistan in a conflict that has come to be known as the “Great Game.”²⁸ Following the establishment of the Soviet Union in 1922, it signed a treaty of neutrality and non-aggression with Afghanistan. After Daud Khan became prime minister in the post-World War II era, he launched the first five-year plan aimed at increasing economic growth in the country, which sought Soviet economic and technical support.²⁹ During this period, the Communist Bloc accounted for 50 percent of Afghanistan’s trade, and Soviet aid to the country also steadily increased. By providing aid worth 515 million USD in the period between 1954 and 1963 as well as military equipment, the Soviets further consolidated their power in the region.³⁰ The Soviet Union did recognise that their power in the region was facilitated by a close relationship with the Afghan government, and any threat to the Afghan government would directly impact Soviet influence. During Daud Khan’s Presidency, his policies, which were described as being neither left nor right but “Daudward” by the US embassy in Kabul,³¹ angered all the factions of Afghan society, especially conservative Islamists. During this period, Afghans studying Islamic studies in Cairo came in contact with the Muslim Brotherhood (*Ikhwanul Muslimeen*), an organisation that advocated for *Tafkirism*, an Islamic doctrine that accuses other Muslims of apostasy of the Islamic faith.³² Leaders like Burhanuddin Rabbani, Sibghatullah Mojaddedi, and Abdul Rabb-ur-Rasul Sayyaf, who were primarily Pashtun (the majority ethnic group) and Tajik, formed the *Jamiat-i-Islam* Party, which denounced Daud Khan’s

policies as atheist and un-Islamic, and they organised anti-government protests. This conservative faction fled to Pakistan following a crackdown on such Islamic dissident activities, where they received support from the government on account of Daud Khan's Pashtunistan policy. While some of them moved their base of operations to Pakistan, many of these factions continued to operate in the Afghan countryside, where they had managed to consolidate power. The Soviet Union, on the other hand, supported Afghanistan's claim over the NWFP and Soviet Premier Bulganin said, "We sympathise with Afghanistan's policy on the question of Pushtunistan."³³ Following the *Saur* Revolution, these leaders started calling for *jihad* or a religious struggle against the PDPA, and during this period a more radical Islamist organisation, called *Hezb-i-Islam*, was formed by Gulbuddin Hekmatyar. The kidnapping of American Ambassador Dubs by Shiite anti-government Muslims and the Herat Uprising further showed the inability of the government to control the situation. In 1979, the Soviets, seeing the overthrow of the Shah of Iran by the Shiite movement led by Ayatollah Khomeini, feared a similar sort of revolution in Afghanistan. Andropov noted, "If we don't support Taraki right now with the use of force, then we might lose Afghanistan; that is, Brzezinski's theory—creating a "green" underbelly below our Central Asian republics—would be realised."³⁴ Moreover, the Soviets were afraid that this Islamic fundamentalism would spill over into central Asia and Caucasia. Thus posing a direct threat to the Soviet Union within its borders. So, the Soviets sanctioned the use of military force to depose Amin and appointed Babrak Karmal as the President of Afghanistan.

Even though the general secretary of the Soviet Communist Party was in favour of the invasion, this is not to say that there was broad consensus in the communist party for the invasion. This is indicated in the following transcript from a politburo meeting:

“[Yuri] Andropov: Comrades, I have thought this issue over very thoroughly since yesterday and have concluded that we should consider very, very seriously whether it would make sense to send troops into Afghanistan. The economy is backward, the Islamic religion predominates, and nearly all of the rural population is illiterate. I do not think we can uphold the revolution in Afghanistan with the help of our bayonets. The idea is intolerable and we cannot risk it.

[Andrei] Gromyko: I fully support Comrade Andropov’s view that we should exclude the dispatch of troops to Afghanistan. The Afghan army is unreliable and our army would become an aggressor. With whom will it fight? With the Afghan people! Our Army would have to shoot them! To be blunt, the Afghan [communist] leaders have made many mistakes and haven’t got the support of their own people.

[Andrei] Kirilenko: Tanks and armoured vehicles cannot rescue them [the PDPA]. I think that we must frankly tell them that. We must say that we will support them to the hilt, we shall give them all of the aid that we have promised to give, but we cannot send troops.”³⁵

This shows that the Soviets did not think very highly of their Afghan comrades and did recognize how an invasion could backfire. However, events within Afghanistan, such as Amin taking over from Taraki and trying to improve relations with the West, made the Soviets change their minds, and they launched the invasion in December 1979.³⁶

Period of Soviet Occupation:

Preparations for the invasion were underway before the official announcement was made, with a Soviet brigade landing at Bagram Air Base, north of Kabul, on December 7 and clearing the highways for the Soviet invasion. On Christmas Eve, the official announcement was made, and the Soviets carried out landings at the Kabul Air Base. By December 27, the Soviet Army had managed to capture *Darulaman Palace*, followed by the Soviet assault on *Tajbeg Palace*, during which Amin was killed. Two motorised divisions started to move from the Soviet border in the north to Kabul and Kandahar. On the military front, the Soviets adopted a policy of attrition by terrorising villages.³⁷ The Soviet Army initially focused on capturing the urban centres; following this, it tried to block the Pakistani and Iranian borders. Using the *Sardandoy*, who were posted in Afghanistan before the invasion, they determined forces within the Afghan Army that were not loyal to them. The Soviet military dearmed these regiments, and when these operations failed, they destroyed these disloyal factions like the 26th Afghan Parachute Regiment with superior military power.³⁸ Within the first six months of 1980, the total number of Soviet troops deployed rose to 81,800, and this number was only to grow in the coming months and years. In Moscow, President Brezhnev, within an hour of the announcement of the formation of the new government by the Kabul Radio, congratulated Karmal and the USSR justified the Soviet invasion, citing Article 51 of the United Nations Charter, which states, “Nothing in the present Charter shall impair the inherent right of individual or collective self-defence if an armed attack occurs against a Member of the United Nations until the Security Council has taken measures necessary to maintain international peace and security.”³⁹ And Article 4 of the friendship treaty, which authorises the use of military force to protect the sovereignty and integrity of the nation.⁴⁰ Moscow also said that it had nothing to do with the removal of Amin and called it a “pure coincidence.”⁴¹ The United States,

in response to the invasion, announced sanctions on the USSR and announced its intention to boycott the 1980 Moscow Summer Olympics.

The period of Soviet involvement in Afghanistan can be divided into four main phases. The first phase was from December 1979 to February 1980, when the Soviet army invaded Afghanistan and set up their garrisons in the country. In the second phase, from March 1980 to April 1985, the Soviet military engaged in active combat with the *Mujahideen* or opposition forces. However, in the third phase of the invasion, which lasted until early 1987, the Soviets reduced military combat and were primarily involved in the protection of military and civilian infrastructure. And in the last phase, the Soviets prepared for the withdrawal from Afghanistan. Each of these phases represents a new relationship between the Soviet and Afghan governments as well as new strategies adopted by the Soviets to counter the *Mujahideen* rebels, who for most of the war controlled 80% of the country's area.⁴²

First Phase of the Soviet-Afghan War: The first phase of the war could be hailed as a Soviet victory, with the Soviets invading and capturing large parts of the urban areas of the country. The Soviets also showed their logistical prowess in this first phase of the war and successfully mobilised the 40th Army, which was to be commanded by the Marshall of the Soviet Union, Sergey Sokolov. 50,000 officers and soldiers from the reserve were activated, and the Turkestan Military District proceeded to cross the Amu Darya River under Colonel General Maksimov.⁴³ The Soviet soldiers entered Afghanistan from Termez and followed the highway from there to Kabul, which passed through the Hindu Kush Mountain Range. Initially, the Soviets, who expected this to be a short war, issued orders to penetrate deep into Afghanistan with special emphasis on the rural parts. However, on December 26th, they were ordered to move to Kabul following the deposition of Amin by the 103rd Guards Airborne Division. The Soviets had been successful in

creating an element of surprise by not only mobilising their troops quickly but also by launching the invasion on Christmas Eve, when Western Intelligence Services were not very alert. In 1980, as resistance to Soviet troops grew, a greater number of soldiers were deployed, and the 40th army consisted of three motorised rifle divisions, an air-borne division, an air assault brigade, and two separate motorised rifle regiments, apart from two separate regiments.⁴⁴ The military was also largely successful in setting up logistical support and garrisons, with some logistic lines or LOCs in Afghanistan being shorter than LOCs inside the Soviet Union. The Soviets had believed that their mere presence would scare all Afghan dissident factions; however, the Soviets were soon going to find out that they were wrong in making this assumption.

Second Phase of the Soviet-Afghan War: The Soviet Army was a traditional army with most of its doctrine created during World War II, or the Great Patriotic War (as the Soviets called it), fighting armies of sovereign countries. The Soviets had little to no combat experience in anti-insurgency and guerilla warfare, this factor along with the difficult terrain led to major Soviet losses in the second phase of the Soviet-Afghan War. In the first phase of the Soviet-Afghan War, the *Mujahideen* used conventional war tactics, but in the second phase, they shifted to guerilla warfare. The *Mujahideen* sought refuge in the rural countryside and in the mountains, where small modules of 15-20 fighters would ambush Soviet convoys as they passed through the *Hindu Kush* Mountains and the *Ragistan* Desert, theatres of operation for which their weapons weren't designed. The *Mujahideen* fighters didn't necessarily look for battlefield supremacy; instead, they aimed to fight for the longest possible time and wear out the Soviet soldiers.⁴⁵ The *Mujahideen* fighters, who came from different socio-ethnic groups, easily merged into the Afghan populace, thus, making it difficult for the Soviets to recognise these fighters. After major Soviet defeats in 1980–81, the Soviets began to extensively use air warfare, primarily the Mi 24 Attack Helicopter

and anti-personnel mines, to counter the *Mujahideen*. They adopted a “scorched-earth” and “migratory genocide” policy of warfare that led to large numbers of civilian casualties and forced many Afghans to flee to Pakistan and Iran.⁴⁶ Under this military strategy, the Soviets destroyed resources to prevent their enemies from using them. The Soviets maintained a force of nearly 600 helicopters in the country.⁴⁷ These weapons of aerial warfare managed to destroy many *Mujahideen* installations across the country, as these rural fighters weren’t trained for combat against helicopters. A British journalist noted that the Mujahidin, “feared them [Mi 24 *Hind*] more than anything else.”⁴⁸ Helicopters were also used to bring fuel, food and other necessary supplies to the units in areas where roads didn’t exist and they were also used to protect Soviet convoys, Thus, helping improve Soviet LOCs.⁴⁹ Lester Grau, a Soviet analyst, noted, “Without the helicopter gunship, the Soviets may have withdrawn years earlier. Its firepower, mobility, and initial invulnerability put the guerrillas on the defensive. The Soviets used helicopters extensively and ruthlessly against the unprotected guerrillas.”⁵⁰ However, these victories in the air did not help significantly reduce casualties on the ground. The Soviet casualties, which totalled 9175 at the end of the second phase,⁵¹ along with the lack of support from the Afghan Army, led to the Soviets adopting a more defensive approach in 1985.

Third Phase of the Soviet-Afghan War: The penultimate phase of the war saw a great decrease in Soviet active combat. The Soviets, who hoped to defeat the opposition guerillas before exiting the nation, had hoped that if they did not attack the *Mujahideen*, the guerilla fighters, who were essentially farmers, would return to agriculture and would not pursue their quest to remove the Soviets from the country. However, the third phase saw no major decrease in the number of attacks from the *Mujahideen*’s side, and these armed fighters continued to attack Soviet installations. Within the Soviet Union itself, there was a lot of opposition to this war, and Mikhail Gorbachev,

unlike Leonid Brezhnev, did not adopt an expansionist policy, instead focusing on economic growth. All these factors led to the first announcement of the Soviet withdrawal of six regiments in July 1986.⁵² At the end of 1986, the US had been supporting the *Mujahideen* from the beginning of the war, supplying them with the stinger missile, which inflicted heavy losses on the Soviets. In a meeting in December 1986, the Central Committee of the PDPA, now under the leadership of Najibullah, decided to undertake a policy of national reconciliation, which involved the incorporation of the Mujahidin in the proposed multi-party democratic framework, recognising that a military solution to this war was not achievable.⁵³ Thus, the third phase paved the way for a complete withdrawal of Soviet troops in the fourth phase.

Fourth Phase of the Soviet-Afghan War: The withdrawal of Soviet troops from Afghanistan was the main event in this last phase of the war. In 1987, the Soviets adopted a policy of not engaging in any active combat or fighting with the *Mujahideen* unless provoked, except Operation Magistral, when the Soviets attacked the *Mujahideen* forces to clear the highway to Paktia, in eastern Afghanistan.⁵⁴ The adoption of this policy was in the wake of growing public awareness within the Soviet Union about growing casualties (despite media censorship) from war veterans (*Afgantsy*) who had returned. But, during this period, *Mujahideen* attacks continued to increase on account of the *Mujahideen* using the Stinger missile that had been supplied to them a year prior. Recognising that national reconciliation was not working, the Soviets sought out a diplomatic method of settlement with Pakistan and the United States to end the dispute. In this effort, a series of four agreements termed the Geneva Accords were signed that aimed to promote friendly relations between Pakistan and Afghanistan as well as between the USSR and the USA, who acted as co-guarantors of the accords.⁵⁵ The negotiations for this agreement had been going on for the previous six years under UN Under-Secretary-General Diego Cordovez. The first agreement

prevented each country from intervening in each other's internal affairs and banned "within its territory the training, equipping, financing, and recruitment of mercenaries from whatever origin for the purpose of hostile activities against the other High Contracting Party [Pakistan and Afghanistan]." ⁵⁶ Therefore, this agreement effectively banned Pakistan and the United States from supporting or arming the *Mujahideen*. The second agreement related to the rights of Afghan refugees who had fled to Pakistan following the invasion, and the third agreement created a timeline for the withdrawal of troops. Half of the Soviet soldiers were to leave Afghanistan by August 15, 1989, and the remaining within nine months of the signing of the agreement. The last agreement was signed by the USSR and the US, which affirmed the "sovereignty, independence, and territorial integrity" of Afghanistan and Pakistan. ⁵⁷ The nine years of the war inflicted significant monetary and military losses on the Soviet Army, with General Alexei Lizichev disclosing that the war led to 13,310 casualties. ⁵⁸ The Soviets had spent 7 billion dollars per year on their activities, ⁵⁹ leading to a total estimate of approximately 70 billion dollars for the invasion. At the time of the withdrawal, there were significant doubts as to the durability of the Najibullah government, as the Geneva Accords did not create a ceasefire and the *Mujahideen* were still steadfast in their goal of deposing the communist government. During their withdrawal, the Soviets left behind most of their equipment for the Afghan military, which is believed to have found its way into the hands of armed insurgents after 1989. The Soviets were repelled from Afghanistan due to a strong internal desire to remain independent as they had been for centuries; this desire is best exemplified in General Abdul Rahim Wardak's words, who said,

"As a nation, we believed that history repeats itself. What happened in the 19th Century to the invading British would also be the fate of the Soviet invaders. Philosophically, the Soviets believed

that history is unidirectional, progressive and does not repeat itself. History did repeat itself and we did prevail.”⁶⁰

Afghan Government Policies During and Right After the Soviet Invasion:

The main objective of the PDPA following the invasion of the Soviet Union was to prevent factionalism within the party and to generate mass appeal for the PDPA. To fulfil the latter goal, Karmal followed a policy of moderation in doing so, trying to lessen the Marxist nature of his party. He also tries to present himself as a devout Muslim and change the face of the party, which had been referred to as “atheist” by the opposition. This is most evident in the first article of the interim constitution, which stated the Democratic Republic of Afghanistan (DRA) was an “independent, democratic state belonging to all Muslim working people of Afghanistan.”⁶¹ He also released 15,000 prisoners in July in order to provide “total amnesty for all those political prisoners who have survived the bloody Amin regime.”⁶² While Karmal did in his early days adopt a policy of unity by appointing *Khalqis* to his cabinet, including Assadullah Sarwari, who had been accused of being Karmal’s second deputy in 1978–79, this did not last. Later, Karmal ordered a purge of *Khalqi* factions from the party, even though they were the majority. In May 1980, he ordered the removal of seven *Khaliqi* army commanders and replaced them with *Parchmites*, following which *Khalqi* military commanders tried to carry out a coup d'etat against Karmal in June, July, and October of that year.⁶³

Throughout this period, the Soviets continued to maintain a high level of control over Afghanistan, providing military aid to the Afghan military and fighting the *Mujahideen* with minimal support

from Afghan troops as a result of the increasing number of desertions within military ranks, with estimates of 1500 to 2000 men deserting every month due to a lack of understanding of the goals of the mission.⁶⁴ The Soviets adopted a three-pronged strategy of depopulating the rural regions to stop the *Mujahideen* advance, exploiting ethno-religious diversity in the country to promote hatred between communities, and remodelling the Afghan Administration to closely resemble the Soviet System.⁶⁵ The Soviets also tried to increase membership in the PDPA (without too much success) and pursued greater economic ties with Afghanistan. As a result of the war, grain production in Afghanistan decreased to one-fifth of pre-war levels, and this shortage was made up for by grains imported from the Soviet Union. The Soviets also provided vocational training to workers, built or repaired industrial facilities, and provided support in the form of aid (which had doubled from the pre-war level) during the war years.

The Afghans and Pakistanis had been negotiating the situation in Afghanistan at talks mediated by the UN since 1980, following the UN General Assembly resolution in November of that year. The Soviet Union wanted the complete elimination of rebel forces, while Pakistan wanted the immediate withdrawal of Soviet troops. However, the Soviet Union under Brezhnev was not going to agree to the withdrawal until the communist government in Kabul was secured and the opposition was neutralised. The irony in this method is that to secure Afghanistan's place in the Soviet bloc, it would have to be completely crushed, which was brought out by Bradsher when he said, "Soviets might have to destroy Afghanistan in order to save it."⁶⁶ So, world leaders were hopeful that when Yuri Andropov came to power, he would withdraw Soviet troops from Afghanistan. But in the short period that Andropov and Chernecko were leaders of the Soviet Union, no major progress was made towards this goal. However, it was only when Mikhail Gorbachev became president in 1985 that major steps started to be taken towards an agreement

and the withdrawal of troops. Mikhail Gorbachev was focused more on *perestroika* or the restructuring of the Soviet economy, and unlike the leaders of other superpowers, he advocated for the political freedom of all nations, which is most evident in his book, *Perestroika: New Thinking for Our Country and the World*, in which he wrote, “it is high time to recognise that the Third World nations have the right to be their own bosses.”⁶⁷ During this period, Karmal was replaced by Najibullah, who pursued another round of UN-mediated talks in Geneva and presented his “new vision” for Afghanistan, which provided a diplomatic solution for dealing with the rebels. These talks and policy moves culminated in the signing of the Geneva Accords in April 1988, following the proclamation made by Gorbachev in February that “an acceptable regime in Kabul is no longer a prerequisite for a Soviet withdrawal,”⁶⁸ and the subsequent Soviet withdrawal by February 1989. Following the withdrawal, the Soviet Union and later the Russian Federation (after the collapse) continued to provide military and economic aid to the Najibullah regime, as did the Pakistanis to the rebel groups; both of these actions were in direct violation of the Geneva Accords. In spite of no support from the Soviet troops and the growing strength of the *Mujahideen*, the DRA government managed to stay in power until April 1992. Four months before the collapse, the Russian Federation had cut off aid to the country, which paralysed the Afghan military and enabled the *Mujahideen* to seize power quickly.⁶⁹ This goes to show that the Afghan government was largely dependent on aid even following the invasion. The collapse of the Afghan government led to the Afghan Civil War, which further destabilised the region and led to the Taliban gaining a foothold in Afghanistan.

The *Mujahideen* Rebels and Operation Cyclone:

In many ways, Western and Iranian support for the Sunni and Shiite rebel forces in Afghanistan was the primary reason behind the *Mujahideen* successfully managing to defeat a full-fledged army. The *Mujahideen* leaders were essentially Islamic clerics who, in the Duad Khan era itself, had started using funding from the Pakistani Inter-Services Intelligence (ISI) to destroy the government. This continued during the period after the *Saur* Revolution, but funding for the *Mujahideen* increased exponentially when the United States, along with other countries like Saudi Arabia and China, started sending aid to train and equip these fighters to bring down the government. This funding started a few months before the Soviet Invasion in July 1979 during the Jimmy Carter Administration on the advice of the National Security Advisor, Zbigniew Brzezinski, and the stated aim of the programme was to “suck the Soviets into a Vietnamese quagmire.”⁷⁰ While the US government and the CIA had a history of diverting funds to support such rebel groups, what was odd is that in this particular case, the US Congress, which had impeded previous attempts to provide aid to rebel fighters like the contra in Nicaragua, readily agreed to supply the aid, with Senator Tsongas and Congressman Don Ritter calling for “effective” US aid to “fight for freedom from foreign domination” despite warnings from officials at the CIA, including Deputy Director John Macmohan, who had cautioned the Congress that too large aid packages may provoke Soviet retaliation against Pakistan and will be subject to leakages and corruption.⁷¹ The Western nations began rallying behind Gulbuddin Hekmatyar, the leader of the *Hezb-e-Islami Gulbuddin* rebel group, who was an Islamic fundamentalist and had during the invasion met Margret Thatcher in London.⁷² In addition to the West, these *Mujahideen* groups were also being supported by wealthy Saudi businessmen like Osama Bin Laden, who had himself taken part in the *jihad* against the Soviet Union.

The Islamic rebels can be divided into the Tehran eight and Peshawar seven groups. The Tehran Eight consisted of eight Shiite rebel factions that were funded by the Islamic Republic of Iran, and they were primarily Hazaras. The Peshawar Seven, on the other hand, was funded by the CIA, the British MI6, and the ISI. It was composed of one Tajik group and six Pashtun groups. However, Tehran's support did wane in 1983 on account of weapons shortages in Iran following the Iran-Iraq war. On the other hand, the US Congress continued to approve aid for Afghanistan, with 280 million dollars being approved for 1985 alone.⁷³ This aid was used to supply the *Mujahideen* with Chinese weapons, plastic mines, Soviet AK-47 rifles, and SA-7 anti-aircraft missiles from the Egyptians, who had adopted a foreign policy of improving ties with the West.⁷⁴ The reason behind supplying the *Mujahideen* with non-US weapons was to maintain plausible deniability. The various Mujahidin factions which were supported by these foreign powers did fight among themselves using ammunition provided to them by these actors, on account of their ethnic differences, thus, while the Mujahidin were able to mount a serious threat to the Soviets, they were never able to form a functioning government, resulting in widespread anarchy.

During the course of the war, the Soviets, to counter the *Mujahideen*, provided concessions to minorities and organised them into militias like the Uzbek militias in the Jowzjan and Balkh regions, which operated in non-Uzbek areas as well and these groups were said to be at the “cutting edge” of Soviet nationality policy in Afghanistan.⁷⁵ In the second phase of the war, the Soviets also used heliborne attacks to stop the rebel advance. This strategy had proven useful for the Soviets until 1986, when, under pressure from congressmen, the CIA supplied the *Mujahideen* with the American stinger missile. This move was successful in crippling Soviet airpower and led to the Soviet defeat, which finally ended in their withdrawal. This aid equipment was supplied to Afghanistan from the FATA (Federally Administered Tribal Areas) region of Pakistan, where,

despite creating multiple border checkpoints, the Soviets could not prevent the flow of arms as the border at that time was not fenced. In addition to aiding the *Mujahideen* with arms, the Americans also helped the *Mujahideen* recruit frustrated Muslim youth from other countries to join them and the Pakistani ISI trained these recruits. Osama Bin Laden was the head recruiter of these international volunteers, and it was with the help of these contacts that he was able to form *Al Qaeda* in 1988. Ahmad Rashid, a Pakistani journalist, summed up the American involvement in recruiting foreign fighters by saying,

“With the active encouragement of the CIA and Pakistan's ISI, who wanted to turn the Afghan *jihad* into a global war waged by all Muslim states against the Soviet Union, some 35,000 Muslim radicals from 40 Islamic countries joined Afghanistan's fight between 1982 and 1992. Tens of thousands more came to study in Pakistani madrassas. Eventually, more than 100,000 foreign Muslim radicals were directly influenced by the Afghan *jihad* .”⁷⁶

The Western intelligence services also supported militant Islamist factions in Central Asia to further destabilise the Soviet Union from within. Aid to the rebels continued even after the Soviet invasion until 1992, when the rebel forces, who had had popular support from the start of the war, succeeded in bringing down the Najibullah government. But, after the end of the Cold War, the United States did not have any strategic interests left in Afghanistan and so stopped its funding of the rebel fighters. The CIA called this 10-year-long operation of funding the *Mujahideen* Operation Cyclone, and it is regarded as the most expensive covert operation, with estimates for US government expenditure exceeding 3 billion dollars.⁷⁷

Socio-Economic Impacts of the Soviet-Afghan War:

Prior to the invasion, the Soviet Union and Afghanistan shared strong economic ties, and Afghanistan supplied a large quantity of its natural gas to the USSR in exchange for military aid. During the war, Soviet military aid increased from 267.6 million rubbles in 1980 to 3.9 billion rubbles in 1989, and while sales from natural gas plateaued, domestic revenue excluding the sale of natural gas rose.⁷⁸ This rise in domestic revenue can be attributed to greater economic integration of the Afghan economy with the Soviet economy, the migration of Soviet skilled labour to Afghanistan, and aid. The PDPA's economic policies involved greater state control of industry, and Soviet-style state farms were established. However, to disrupt the Mujahideen economy, the military forces regularly raided and destroyed these farms in the rural areas, which led to a deterioration of agricultural productivity, thus leading to greater reliance on Soviet food exports, in stark contrast to the state of partial self-reliance that had been reached prior to the invasion. In order to facilitate greater Soviet involvement in the economy, the PDPA government let the value of the Afghani fall in comparison to the US dollar, thus making it difficult for bilateral trade with the West, and worked towards developing Soviet-Afghan ventures, with such ventures constituting 75% of state industry.⁷⁹

The war led to significant material and personnel losses, which was the primary cause behind the low growth rates during the war. The material loss is estimated at nearly 12 billion dollars, which includes losses in agriculture, industry, land, transportation, health, education, service industries, infrastructure, and the exploitation of natural gas.⁸⁰ The lack of tourism and trade led to a decrease in foreign exchange, and due to the greater reliance on exports, inflation rose. The war led to nearly 1 million civilian casualties and led to over 5 million Afghans emigrating to Pakistan and Iran to take refuge. Economic inequality also skyrocketed, with the top 6% of earners holding 49% of the capital city's wealth, and poverty was rampant, with the per capita GNP declining to 250 USD.⁸¹

The war led to a number of injuries on account of land mines, and the rise of orthodox Islamic organisations led to a significant worsening of the rights of women.

Recognising growing public dissent against these typically communist economic policies, a number of changes were made as part of the policy of national reconciliation. The Najibullah government, in contrast to the policies of the Karmal regime, worked towards developing public-private partnerships, and guarantees of landownership were embedded in the constitution. In summary, the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan led to a significant decrease in social indicators among the people of Afghanistan and had disastrous impacts on the Afghan economy.

Consequences of the Soviet-Afghan War:

In the aftermath of the Soviet-Afghan War, Western analysts were doubtful about the ability of the Najibullah regime to continue to remain in power without Soviet support. However, the country did not immediately fragment, with the PDPA remaining in power until April 1992. Following the fall of the DRA, several *Mujahideen* groups, with the notable exception of Gulbuddin Hekmatyar, entered into an alliance. These *Mujahideen* groups were divided on ethnic grounds, and the interim government formed under the rotating presidency of Mojaddedi and Rabbani failed to remain in power due to factionalism and attacks from Hekmatyar.⁸² During the period preceding the fall of the Afghan government, the Soviet Union also faced a growing threat of disintegration following the August 1991 coup attempt and the Ukrainian independence referendum. During the Gorbachev era, on account of political liberalisation and separation of the Soviet Military and the Communist Party under the *Perestroika* doctrine, the power of the Communist Party weakened, ultimately leading to the fall of the Berlin Wall and the subsequent collapse of the USSR in December 1991.⁸³ The Soviet involvement in Afghanistan might have played a role in this collapse, which, along

with the instability in Afghanistan it caused, which continues to date, further underscores the impact the war had on the world.

The Collapse of the Soviet Union: The Soviet Invasion of Afghanistan adversely affected the military establishment and highlighted the heterogeneity within the Soviet Union, which is best brought out by Hassan Kakkar when he said, “The Afghan adventure was not the Soviets' only adventure, but it was their last.”⁸⁴ Soviet leaders before Gorbachev extensively used the military to maintain unity within the USSR, with the military being used in the past to quell revolts in Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, and Kyrgyzstan. The losses suffered by the Soviet military in this war led to questions from leaders in Moscow regarding the efficacy of the military, which were further compounded following the condemnation of the invasion by Gorbachev and Shevardnadze, the foreign minister, referring to the invasion as a sin. During the war years, Tajik mullahs began to issue statements against the invasion, claiming that “the Soviets are turning Afghans into *kafirs* (infidels).”⁸⁵ In other parts of Central Asia, there were anti-war protests, and this quickly spread to European Soviet Socialist republics as well. In Lithuania, *Ausra*, an underground newspaper pointed out that “Ukrainians, Estonians, Latvians, [and] Lithuanians” were being forced to “obey the brutal orders of the Russian officers and shed both their own and Afghan blood.”⁸⁶ Ukrainian Catholic activists also wrote to the Soviet Defence Minister, Dimitri Ustinov, stating that “Ukrainians do not wish to fight, nor do they want this unjust war,” and in Yerevan, there was a huge protest by the parents of soldiers who were fighting the war.⁸⁷ With the idea of *Glasnost* being promulgated by Gorbachev, common Soviet media outlets also started publishing news about the real cost of the Soviet invasion and the state of the *Afgantsy*. The *Afgantsy* following their return were ignored by the media and the polity and were not given any assistance in finding employment and obtaining housing and medical care. These *Afgantsy* had ethical dilemmas

regarding the Soviet operations, with one soldier noting, “There were things we’re ashamed to remember,” and these experiences led to them discrediting the morality of the military apparatus.⁸⁸ Therefore, the Soviet invasion drew the different institutions and peoples within the USSR further apart, leading to its collapse.

Afghan Civil War: Following the Soviet departure, the United Nations sent Ben Savon to mediate discussions between the *Mujahideen* factions and the Najibullah government to create a broad-based government.⁸⁹ However, these talks failed, and just as Najibullah was going to resign following the reduction of aid, Ahmad Shah Massoud entered Kabul. He was the Tajik *Mujahideen* Commander, closely associated with Rabbani’s *Jamiat-i-Islam*, who had managed to defend the Panjshir Valley from the Soviets despite seven attempted invasions. Massoud, along with General Adil Rashid Dostam, who had defected from the communist regime, formed an alliance and managed to capture large parts of Kabul. After capturing Kabul, most of the *Mujahideen* groups agreed to form an interim government with a rotating presidency. While Mojaddedi resigned when his term ended, Rabanni did not; this, along with infighting among the *Mujahideen* groups, further escalated the situation. Over time, relations between Massoud and Dostam also started to worsen, ultimately leading to Dostam joining hands with Gulbuddin Hekmatyar’s *Hezb-e-Islami*, who had not joined the interim government. The combined forces of Hekmatyar and Dostam blockaded the city and carried out several missile and airborne attacks on the city in 1994, which forced nearly 600,000 people to flee Kabul and earned Hekmatyar the title of “Butcher of Kabul.”⁹⁰ The Hazara Organisation *Wahdat* also controlled some parts of Kabul, and the fighting between the two main coalitions waged on in other parts of the country as well. In that year, Rabbani made efforts to come to a settlement by advocating for the organisation of a *loya jirgah*, composed of members from all the *Mujahideen* factions, to elect the new leaders and make an interim parliament. The

United Nations also sent Mahmoud Mistry of Tunisia to constitute an Afghan Advisory Council to come up with the terms of the settlement, but the proposals of the Advisory Council were never adopted as a UN peace plan, and the fighting never came to an end.⁹¹ During this period, another Pashtun organisation from Kandahar called the *Taliban*, composed of Islamic leaders and students of Islam from madrassas, became stronger. They managed to capture the territory held by the *Hezbi-Islami*, Herat, from Ismail Khan, a pro-Rabbani leader and pressed on the Masoud-Rabbani forces in Kabul. While General Dostam did tacitly support the *Taliban*, he, along with the other members of his coalition, feared a *Taliban* takeover.⁹² Towards late 1995, the northern parts of the country were controlled by General Dostam; Kabul and some other scattered parts were under the control of Massoud, while the *Taliban*, under the leadership of Mullah Omar, had captured most parts of the country. During this period, the former ruler Zahir Shah also sent his envoy, Sardar Wali, to ascertain whether conditions were favourable for his return to Afghanistan from exile to once again become king.⁹³ However, following the capture of Kabul by the *Taliban* in 1996, the group firmly asserted its power over Afghanistan and controlled Afghanistan for the next five years.

Rise of Terrorism in Afghanistan: The *Taliban* regime was characterised by its belief in an interpretation of the Sharia Law that prevented women from working or being educated. Social indicators in Afghanistan significantly worsened, and the *Taliban* carried out systematic persecution of the Hazara community and arrested or assassinated *Mujahideen* who opposed their rule. The *Taliban* regime was supported by the Pakistani government, which supplied the *Taliban* with monetary aid,⁹⁴ and the United States, which had played an important role in supporting the *Mujahideen* fighters during the invasion, stopped providing any support to these groups and denounced the *Taliban* annexation while the ammunition supplied by them was still being used by

the *Mujahideen* groups, including the *Taliban*. During this period, Afghanistan became a safe haven for Osama Bin Laden. However, the *Taliban* officially denied this claim, and Mullah Ehsanullah Ehsan, a *Taliban Shura* Member, told American diplomats, “If his presence is located in areas under our control, we will definitely impose a ban on his activities.”⁹⁵ The *Taliban* also aided the Haqqani Network and the Islamic Movement of Uzbekistan, both of which were either financed by or had strong ties to *Al Qaeda*.⁹⁶ On August 7, 1998, *Al Qaeda* carried out an attack on the US embassies in Dar es Salaam and Nairobi, which drew the US government’s attention towards the *Al Qaeda* presence in *Taliban*-ruled Afghanistan. In response to the attack, the US carried out Operation Infinite Reach, in which terrorist installations in Afghanistan and Sudan were bombed.⁹⁷ In the period between the 9/11 attack and this operation, the elusive Mullah Omar tried contacting US officials in an attempt to establish better relations, which was possibly an immediate reaction to the strikes. The *Taliban* continued to rule Afghanistan till they were ousted by the combined forces of a coalition of countries, including the United States, in Operation Enduring Freedom following the September 11 terrorist attack for aiding *Al Qaeda*, who were behind the attack. While the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan was not a direct cause of the rise of terrorism in the country, the *Mujahideen* fighters established a tradition of religious struggle or *jihad* during their fight against the Soviet occupation, a concept that these terrorist groups used to carry out these attacks.

Outcomes:

The Soviet involvement ravaged Afghanistan. Many international laws of armed conflict were broken by both sides, the Soviets and the *Mujahideen* groups. The Soviets resorted to retributive mass killings, especially in rural areas, and their policy of “migratory genocide,” by which the

Soviets dropped butterfly mines from helicopters, led to a number of civilian casualties. These human rights violations and accusations of arbitrary arrest have led to claims that the Soviets carried out a genocide in Afghanistan. The *Mujahideen* groups, which were aided by the United States, whose foreign policy was said to be “rooted in moral values” by Jimmy Carter, carried out human rights violations of their own, including killings of government officials and rival clan leaders.⁹⁸ Torture was commonly reported in *Mujahideen* prisons, and they controlled the population with the authority of the gun. Thus, mass killings and restrictions on basic rights by both sides led to Afghanistan scoring very low on Human Development Indices in the 1980s and '90s.⁹⁹

The broad learnings that can be drawn from the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan can be broadly split into military and non-military conclusions. On the military front, the Soviets realised their shortcomings in counter-insurgency and guerilla warfare, which was the primary reason behind the high casualties. The Soviet army’s fighting techniques following World War II had become attuned to fighting with conventional armies, and their performance indicates that they had forgotten their experience of combat with guerilla rebels during the Basmachi Revolution in the 1930s. Most of the Soviet troops fighting the war were from Central Asia, and the administration had hoped to win the support of the locals by using troops who had the same ethnicity; however, Thomas Hammond, in analysing the impact of this strategy, said,

“There is no evidence to indicate that the Afghans found the invasion any more palatable just because some of the Soviet soldiers were ethnic and religious brothers. Furthermore, the fraternisation appears to have worked against the USSR rather than for it, resulting in sympathy for the Afghans among Soviet soldiers rather than sympathy for the Soviet Union among Afghans.”¹⁰⁰

The Soviet military also had a firm centralisation of authority and control in their military apparatus, which backfired in counter-insurgency operations in Afghanistan. Another problem that came to the forefront during the war was the lack of career NCOs in the Soviet military. Most soldiers were conscripts who served their required period in the military, and very few conscripts chose to serve as extended service personnel, which led to a general degradation in the quality of Soviet troops. Thus, junior officers were performing the role of soldiers instead of assuming an administrative role. In addition to these points, the war also demonstrated the need for greater flexibility, especially in logistics, to ensure the smooth working of supply chains.

The difficulties the Soviets faced in capturing the whole country also demonstrate Afghanistan's unique geographical position, making it difficult for any invading army to annex the country. The northern parts of the country, the Pakistan Border in the north-east, and the Wakhan Corridor, which forms the border with China, are largely mountainous terrain of the Hindu Kush Mountains, making it very difficult for an aggressor to attack. The border with Iran is an inhospitable arid zone, and the southern border with Pakistan is a desert. The southwestern part of Afghanistan also consists of many rivers, like the Helmand and Farah Rivers, which further make invasion difficult. Afghanistan also experiences extreme weather conditions, especially in the winter, and being a landlocked country, there is no scope for a naval invasion. These factors support the local armed clans or rebel forces, as they often have a better understanding of the geography than a foreign army.

The use of proxies by the two rival factions, also gives us important insights about the unregulated use of such actors. Proxies cannot be thought of as just actors of their parent states, but do have their own free agency which can have catastrophic impacts when misused. In the context of the war, this phenomenon is best represented by the evolution of groups like *Al Qaeda* and the *Taliban*

from anti-Soviet fighters to terrorists who went on to endanger US and allied interests around the globe. Therefore, while the US was successful in achieving their short-term outcomes, the success of the policies used to counter the Soviets ultimately backfired, emphasizing the importance of ideological similarity over a *realpolitik* approach in selecting vassal actors during war.

Conclusion:

Cold War literature often simplifies the role of the proxy to merely that of a client of the patron state, however, it is important to recognize their own autonomy in conducting their own affairs and the role this has in shaping conflict.¹⁰¹ In the Soviet-Afghan war, the action of Amin following coming to power directly went against the interests of the Soviet Union which had been supporting the communist party in Afghanistan. Further, the Herat uprising was purely a product of PDPA policies and not that of Soviet actions, demonstrating how the unpopularity of the PDPA was an important motivation for regular civilians to rise up during the war.

It is also important to note that the Afghan *Mujahideen* forces were not just created by Pakistani and Western intelligence forces. The idea of *Jihad* long predates the Soviet invasion, and the rebels who later formed the *Mujahideen* had been in existence since the Daud Khan regime. The rise of the *Mujahideen* forces can be attributed to the lack of popular support for the government of the DRA and an effort by successive leaders of the DRA to distance themselves and the government from Islam. The PDPA thrust progressive marriage and land reform policies into an Islamic conservative nation and arrested members of the traditional elite and religious establishment, which led to the growth of extremism in Afghanistan. Therefore, it is likely that Islamic fundamentalism in Afghanistan was probably a reaction to domestic policies, while foreign interference played a major role in the growth of the movement.

That being said, the *Mujahideen* themselves, like the PDPA, were not completely united. While they had similar short-term objectives, their ideologies and methods varied widely. These differences came to the fore during the Afghan Civil War. This disunity is a product of varying demographic identities resulting from geographical divides within Afghanistan and the central position of Afghanistan leading to the migration of various ethnicities. While this did create confusion for the Soviet armies marching into the country, leading to large scale losses, it has also prevented the establishment of permanent peace and harmony.

Afghanistan stands to be an example of a nation seared in the flames of the depredation of opposing regional interest groups. The continuous war and strife in the country since the 1970s has devastated the people of Afghanistan and destabilised a region with great potential in mining. The war also underscores Abdul Haq's poignant observation, "Afghanistan is a graveyard of empires," while at the same time bringing out that the biggest threat to Afghan sovereignty and unity is not from foreign aggressors but from factionalism based on ethnicity within the country, which has plagued the nation right since its inception.

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